

OPTISOICHEM

“OPTimized conversion of residual wheat straw
to bio-ISObutene for bio based CHEMicals”

Grant Agreement n° 744330 –
Innovation Action-Demonstration Project

Deliverable D3.11

**3rd report on the delivery of several tons of 2G isobutene,
according to program, with full characterization**

Start date of the project: 1st June 2017

Duration: 67 months

Project Coordinator: Bernard Chaud – Global Bioenergies (P1 - GBE)

Contact: Bernard Chaud – Global Bioenergies (P1 - GBE) - Bernard.Chaud@global-bioenergies.com

Document Classification

Title	3 RD REPORT ON DELIVERY OF FIRST 2G ISOBUTENE TON
Deliverable	D3.11
Reporting Period:	3
Date of Delivery foreseen in DoA	31 12 2022
Actual Date of Delivery to JU	31 01 2023
Authors	Bernard Chaud, P1, GBE
Work package	WP3 SCALE-UP OF BIO-IBN PRODUCTION
Dissemination	PU=Public
Nature	R: Document, report
Version	V0
Doc ID Code	D3.11_OPTISOCHEM_P1_GBE_230119
Keywords	Report, pilot plant, 2G substrate, bio IBN sample

Document History

Partner	Remark	Version	Date
P1_GBE	Draft Version	1	19/01/2023
P1_GBE	Draft Version		
P1_GBE	Final Version	2	15/02/2023

Document Validation

Partner	Approval (Signature or e-mail reference)
P1_GBE	Bernard.chaud@global-bioenergies.com

This project has received funding from the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 744330.

Document Abstract

This report is the third of a series of 3 which describes the evolving status of the fermentative bio-IBN production towards the ton scale target alongside the project duration. Because of the public (PU) nature of this deliverable, details such as WSH composition, strain genotype and process parameters will not be disclosed in this document.

Various WSH grades and IBN producing strains have been tested at the lab scale and the best combinations were transferred for scale up to P1-GBE's Pilot Plant facility at Pomacle-Bazancourt (France). This work resulted notably in the production of the first 2G isobutene kilogram from P2-CLA's Wheat Straw Hydrolysate (WSH), as described in a previous public report published at M12 (Deliverable D3.1). Additional kilograms were produced at the pilot plant afterwards.

Then the process was transferred to GBE's Demo Plant facility in Leuna (Germany). This facility includes a fermentation unit comprising a 500L seed fermenter and a 5000L production fermenter, a purification unit allowing for IBN purification and condensation and a storage unit. Scale-up runs at the Demo scale in Leuna with WSH started in Q4 2018.

During year 2021, GBE transferred the 5000L vessel from Leuna to Pomacle-Bazancourt so as to pool together Pilpot and Demo operations. Demo activities during RP3 were executed partly in Leuna, partly in Pomacle.

During the project duration, 202 IBN-production fermentation runs were executed by P1-GBE, either at pilot scale or at demo scale, either with WSH substrate or with benchmark substrate, either for the project activities or for out-of-project activities.

Bio-IBN was delivered by P1-GBE to P3-INE for experimentation. During the project duration, Bio-IBN was also delivered by P1-GBE to other places for out-of-project activities.

This report displays the bio-IBN quantities that were produced and the outcome of these quantities as well as it states the achievement of Milestone 12.

The information contained in this report is subject to change without notice and should not be construed as a commitment by any members of the OPTISOCEM Consortium. The OPTISOCEM Consortium assumes no responsibility for the use or inability to use any procedure or protocol which might be described in this report. The information is provided without any warranty of any kind and the OPTISOCEM Consortium expressly disclaims all implied warranties, including but not limited to the implied warranties of merchantability and fitness for a particular use.

Table of Contents

Document Abstract.....	3
<i>Abbreviations</i>	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Production of bio-IBN at 500L & 5000L scales	6
2.1. Strain and protocol development in the P&-GBE's Evry laboratory	6
2.2. The bio-IBN pilot plant and Demo Plant	6
2.3. Bold lines of the IBN production process.....	8
2.4. Production at Pilot scale and Demo scale.....	8
2.5. Analysis of 2G IBN.....	9
3. Bio-IBN deliveries.....	10
4. Conversion of bio-IBN to PIBs, DIB, TIB and TeIB	10
5. Conclusions	11

Abbreviations

GBE: Global Bioenergies

IBN: Isobutene or isobutylene

WSH: Clariant's Wheat Straw Hydrolysate

TPED: Transportable Pressure Equipment Directive

PIB: Polyisobutylène ou Polyisobutène

DIB: Diisobutylène ou Diisobutène

TIB : Triisobutylène

TeIB : Tetraisobutylène

HMF: Hydroxymethylfurfural

RP1: Reporting Period 1

RP2: Reporting Period 2

RP3: Reporting Period 3

1. Introduction

This report is the 3rd a series of 3 (D3.4 was delivered in 2019, D3.10 delivered July 2020) which describes the evolving status of the WSH-based bio-IBN production towards the ton scale target alongside the project duration. Because of the public (PU) nature of this deliverable, details such as WSH composition, strain genotype and process parameters will not be disclosed in this document.

P1-GBE develops an IBN production process by fermentation, allowing for the conversion of sugars into gaseous IBN. The fermentation gas is purified and condensed, in order to recover highly concentrated IBN in pressurized cylinders. P2-CLA has delivered more than 52 tons of WSH to P1-GBE in order to assess the current production process of this feedstock, and to develop new IBN producing microbes, adapted for WSH fermentation.

Activities to modify WSH production process were performed at P2-CLA (Planegg & Straubing) and activities to adapt IBN-producing microbe to WSH were performed at P1-GBE's research facility based in Evry. The objective was to optimize the simultaneous consumption of the different sugars present in WSH, and to overcome the inhibitory effect of impurities such as HMF and furfural and additional inhibiting impurities which were identified during the project such as phenolic compounds, including hydroquinone and hydroxycinnamic acid. Process development is first conducted at the lab scale (1 and 10 litres bioreactors) to test and maximize IBN production with the 1G-type strains as well as with WSH-adapted strains. Second, new strains are transferred to pilot and to demo scale to demonstrate the performances that were achieved at lab scale.

The first conditioning of IBN from WSH was conducted in P1-GBE's Pilot Plant facility at Pomacle-Bazancourt (France). This work resulted notably in the production of the first 2G isobutene kilogram from WSH, as described in a previous public report (Deliverable D3.1). Further activity at Pomacle, resulted in additional bio-IBN produced and bottled with WSH as a feedstock but also with other 2G-type substrates or traditional substrates (out of the scope of this project).

For production at the ton scale, the process was transferred to P1-GBE's Demo Plant facility in Leuna (Germany). This facility includes a fermentation unit comprising a 500L seed fermenter and a 5000L production fermenter, a purification unit allowing for IBN purification and condensation and a storage unit. It is hosted and operated by the Fraunhofer CBP.

Whereas GBE's IBN production process remains today significantly less stable with WSH than with first generation sugars, it was expected from both, the performances at lab scale and pilot scale on WSH on the one hand, and from the benchmarking at the 5000L scale with first generation sugars (not shown in this public report) on the other hand, that the demo plant could run satisfactorily with WSH. Thus, WSH-based runs at the Demo scale in Leuna started in Q4 2018. (Deliverable D3.4)

2. Production of bio-IBN at 500L & 5000L scales

2.1. Strain and protocol development in the P1-GBE's Evry laboratory

Strain genotype and detailed process are confidential information. Basically, P1-GBE's strain for IBN production have an IBN metabolic pathway, introduced into a bacterial chassis derived from the *E. coli* MG1655 bacteria, and modified in order to increase yield. The metabolic pathway can convert the pivotal acetyl-CoA molecule, a central intermediate in metabolism, into IBN, through a cascade of enzymatic reactions performed by a series of recombinant enzymes. These recombinant enzymes include natural enzymes as well as evolved biocatalysts, generated by P1-GBE's enzyme engineering platform, and catalysing non-naturally occurring reactions.

2.2. The bio-IBN pilot plant and Demo Plant

P1-GBE has constructed and commissioned a 500 litres Pilot Plant in 2014 at Pomacle near Reims, France. This plant was designed for a production capacity of 10 t of IBN per year. The plant including a fermentation unit and a purification unit was described in a previous report (Deliverable D3.1).

A highly automated Demo Plant was constructed and commissioned in 2016 at Leuna near Leipzig, Germany (see Figure 1). Designed for a production capacity of 100t of IBN per year, this facility includes a fermentation unit comprising a 500L seed fermenter and a 5000L production fermenter, a purification unit allowing for IBN purification and condensation and a storage unit (Figure 2). It is hosted and operated by the Fraunhofer CBP. On year 2021, GBE started to transfer the demo equipment from Leuna to Pomacle so as to "pool" pilot and demo activities together (hereunder figure 2)

Figure 1. The 5000 litres IBN demo-plant in Leuna (Germany).

Figure 2. The 5000 litres IBN demo-plant transferred in Pomacle (France).

Figure 2. Process scheme of the IBN demo-plant.

The plant includes a fermentation and a purification unit as described in Figure 2. Besides that, a Cleaning-In-Place (CIP) equipment as well as the pre and post treatment (i.e. HTST, surge and killing tank, centrifuge) equipment are present. The fermentation unit comprises a Seed fermenter and a Production fermenter, a series of satellite tanks for substrate, additives,

basic, acids and cleaning solutions. The purification unit comprises a washing column (CWC), adsorption and desorption columns and a final storage and product recovery system

2.3. Bold lines of the IBN production process

As for the smaller scales, pre-cultures are prepared in Erlenmeyer flasks, in parallel, the clean fermenter is prepared with fermentation medium and sterilized, instrumentation (pH, DO, gas analysis) is calibrated, and safety systems are checked.

Upon inoculation, the growth phase is conducted in a fed-batch mode, in order to reach the desired biomass concentration and physiological state. When the cell density reaches a certain level, the broth is transferred to the Production fermenter in order to continue growing the cells until the plateau phase is reached. At this stage, the production phase is initiated, and several process parameters are adapted in order to optimize and stabilize IBN production.

IBN is gaseous at the operating temperatures, and exits in the fermentation off-gas, which is sent to the purification unit.

In Demo scale purification unit, the off-gas is first washed from the fermentation material that could potentially be carried over. The IBN is then adsorbed in a solvent in a first column and, after that, desorbed in a second column, condensed and stored. Condensation occurs at a temperature below the boiling point of IBN, but high enough to avoid the condensation of other remaining gases.

When needed, the liquefied IBN is recovered in pressurized TPED cylinders allowing for shipping.

2.4. Production at Pilot scale and Demo scale

During the total duration of the project, a total of 202 runs were conducted as from the start of the project either at pilot or demo scale, either for Optisochem, or out-of-project according to following Table 1:

	OPTISOICHEM			OUT OF PROJECT			TOTAL		
	Pilot	Demo	Total Optisochem	Pilot	Demo	Total out of Project	Pilot	Demo	Grand Total
RP1 ¹	11	3	14	10	10	20	22	13	35
RP2	15	7	22	16	32	48	31	39	70
RP3	10	8	18	40	39	79	50	47	97
TOTAL	36	18	54	66	81	147	103	99	202

Table 1: Number of runs at pilot scale and Demo scale

¹ RP = Reporting Period

Furthermore, 45 runs were conducted with 2G-type substrate in total, 25 for Optisochem and 20 for out-of-the-project activities, the rest being conducted with benchmark traditional type substrates:

In total, during these 202 runs, more than 10.9 tons of fermentative IBN were produced among which more than 1000 kg out of 2-G type substrate. **Thus achieving MS 12**

For Optisochem, WSH-based runs were more productive at pilot scale compared to the Demo scale for IBN production. As a matter of fact, during RP1 and RP2, 2 main technical issues were encountered at Demo scale that could be alleviated at pilot scale:

- Clogging of substrate flowmeter (leading to WSH feeding arrest) was observed for the first two runs, linked with the handling of the WSH substrate. Such clogging, as well as fouling, has been observed previously at the Pilot scale (500L, Pomacle) but could then be alleviated.
- Contaminations were observed, rather late for the first run and earlier for the second one, and we believe that our standard cleaning was not adequate for the clogged lines and should be improved for such feedstock.

Hopefully, during RP3, these issues were also alleviated at demo scale with the modified hydrolysate process and the 2 step protocol.

2.5. Analysis of 2G IBN

Analysis have been realized on the WSH-based IBN: IBN content after normalization was 99.91% and the detected impurities are listed in Table 2. Sulphur compounds and oxygenates were identified as impurities that need to be strictly controlled for PIBs or Oligomers production. Furthermore, some solvent coming from the purification process was found in the Demo-plant-produced bio-IBN during RP1 (this does not deter from converting the bio-IBN into PIBs or Oligomers but could affect the quality of end-products): fortunately, this issue could be fixed during RP2.

During RP2 further analyses were done so as to compare the quality of the WSH-based IBN to the benchmark-based IBN. The comparison of results of analyses allowed to acknowledge that both IBN grades contain the same type and same amount of impurities: as a result, the benchmark-based IBN is representative for the WSH-based IBN and for other fermentative IBN.

This allowed the project to proceed with downstream activities as described in here under § 3.

Compound	Comment
Purification process solvent	These impurities were skipped during RP2
Sulphur compounds	DMD, DMDS
Oxygenates	acetone, tert-Butanol, ethyl-methyl-ketone, methanol
Water	Skipped during RP3 at the Pomacle set-up
Other Hydrocarbons	< 0,1 %

Table 2. Impurities identified in the bio- IBN from the Demo-plant.

3. Bio-IBN deliveries

During RP1 (June 2017 to December 2018), P1-GBE, delivered 1st kg of IBN to P3-INE (Milestone 4)

During RP2 (January 2019 to June 2020), P1-GBE, delivered to P3-INE the following quantities, thus achieving **Milestone 05**:

- Delivery of more than 100 kg of benchmark bio-IBN at Lavera for experimentation regarding PIBs production: experimentation took place at INE during January 2020.
- Delivery of more than 3 kg of WSH-based-IBN at Köln for further experimentation regarding
- conversion to oligomers: experimentation was postponed to RP-3 due to Covid-19 Crisis.

During RP3(July 2020 to December 2022), P1-GBE delivered to P3-INE the following quantities:

- Delivery of more than 100 kg of fermentative bio-IBN at Lavera for experimentation for PIBs production experimentation
- Delivery of 15 kg of fermentative IBN at Köln for additional experimentation regarding conversion to oligomers

Furthermore, P1-GBE delivered also the quantities displayed in hereunder §4, as out-of-the-project activities.

4. Deliveries of bio-IBN for the conversion to PIBs, DIB, TIB and TeIB

Out of project, bio-IBN conversion activities consisted in renting and running an experimental oligomerisation/etherification set-up from Fraunhofer-CBP-Leuna until December 2019 and from French-based company located in Lyon as from year 2020.

Since the start-up of Optisochem, more than 8 tons of bio-IBN were delivered to one or the other experimental oligomerization set-up. More than 500 kg during RP1, more than 600 kg during RP2, more than 7 000 kg during RP3.

These activities allowed to produce more than 500 kg of bio-DIB and more than 3 800 kg of bio-TIB and more than 600 kg of bio-TelB. Additional quantities were either ETBE or other types of oligomers, or loss.

Among the 500 kg of bio-DIB, 3 batches were reserved for analysis (report from Activation CHA5-LA170, see results synthesis hereunder), displaying, after separation from non-reacted bio-IBN and from TIB, an average value of 2,2,4-trimethylpentene content > 99.8% m/m and 2,2,4-trimethylpenten-1 content > 76% m/m, thus **achieving Milestone 08** :

	Mass (kg)	2,2,4-trimethylpentene content (% m/m GC/FID)	2,2,4-trimethylpenten-1 content (% m/m GC/FID)
D1	11.9	99.8	76.1
D2	17.2	99.9	76.3
D3	18.8	99.9	75.8
Average	47.9	99.9	76.05
MS 08	NA	99.8	76

Table 3: bio-DIB analysis results

5. Conclusions

Thanks to successful runs at Pilot scale on WSH and benchmark substrate, in combination with successful runs at Demo scale, the project could deliver :

On total, P1-GBE could deliver more than 10 tons of fermentative bio-IBN out of which 1 ton of fermentative IBN was produced on 2G type substrate thus delivering **Milestone 12**

The quality of the product was assessed by the recipients and is dealt with in Deliverable D6.5 (Stakeholder evaluation report)